

FROM CARE TO EDUCATION AN ORPHANAGE FOR DISABLED CHILDREN

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Abstract: *Children with disabilities, especially those with multiple disabilities, are often perceived by community as suffering from a disease. They are treated similar to treatments for those patients in the hospital with nurse assistance. Though in practice many of children with disabilities are self-reliant. Several years ago the daily routines of children in care was very monotonous with minimal activity. From morning until evening the children spent most of their time in their bedroom, only occasionally were the children able to enjoy the outside environment. In 2013, we shifted from children with patient based treatment to more educational based programs. We are optimizing the services with current human resources available in the center. We gradually meet the educational needs of the children. Staffs were recruited initially as caregivers before being retraining as educators. Additionally, it is very encouraging for the caregivers to be given the opportunity to become educators. As this has meant for their future career. To help us meet the target of the professional criteria of an educator we have enlisted the support of Perkins International. We are very pleased with the educational activities that have been promoted, children have begun to show huge amounts of progress - especially children who initially required full assistance in all developmental and functional activities. The help offered to children during activities is increasingly minimized as children gain learning experience and confidence. At present, during a few activities some children are no longer in need of any assistance. Our children have grown and now even take part in areas of work which previously were only done by adults. Now our children have become the growing, educationally aware focal point during each activity.*

INTRODUCTION

The Constitution of The Republic of Indonesia has clearly stated that one of the nation's mission statement is to improve the Intellectual life (education) of the people. State and its people are required to work hand in hand and participated in order to improve the quality of Intellectual life in Indonesia.

Education in Indonesia, in an ideal condition, should be enjoyed by all level of society without looking at their status, existence, race and religion. But in reality, Education, specifically for low income household/families with disabilities is still unattainable; one of the reasons is, the parents/families of children with disabilities have limited financial resources to provide the education needed for their children.

One of the dominant factors of the high cost of Sekolah Luar Biasa (School for persons with Disabilities) is because Sekolah Luar Biasa (school for

disabilities) has different type of educators (teachers) compared to that of regular schools. The teachers at Sekolah Luar Biasa have a different qualification, expertise and ability to care and educate person with disability. In addition of the high cost, the limited capacity of students within a class (compared to regular school classes) and the limited number of educators/teachers with the needed qualification is what makes the School for disabilities is expensive. Beside the factors mentioned above, the number of School for disabilities is limited and that makes a person/children with disabilities is unable to access/attend the School for disabilities or Sekolah Luar Biasa.

If seen from the welfare point of view, the welfare of the children with disabilities in Indonesia is far from sufficient. Meanwhile, on the other hand, the increasing numbers of person/children with disabilities have raised the urgency to provide educational,

rehabilitation and health facility that specifically adjusted with the needs of person/children with disabilities.

Realizing the minimum access and services needed for the person/children with disabilities, Yayasan Sayap Ibu, while in the beginning only focusing on in-house care and treatment within our facility for person/children with disabilities, we now start with our own rehabilitation services program, an integrated care with educational program for person/children with disabilities. Our commitment is to create a strong and sustainable educational program and services for person/children with disabilities.

As an institution servicing almost 70% (percent) of person/children with multiple disabilities, it is not an easy thing to do to create an integrated services program which consists of providing care services, therapy and education. In addition to that is the society's view towards person/children with disability.

Since its establishment in 2005, our services towards children with disabilities have not drastically changed, with minimum activities and services, the children tend to be passive and only be treated as an object. The task of caregivers that accompanies the children with disabilities does not differ much compared to the ones that worked in regular household as a helper/maid, and therefore it is seen as not favorable and an unattractive line of work.

In 2014, our historical journey began. An International institution that helped us, gave us a new mindset and insight, from the caregivers, managerial staff to the organizational board of management in Yayasan Sayap Ibu. We understand that children with disabilities should have equal rights and opportunities as those given to normal children. They deserve to have their own opinion, contribute in social life, and also have the right to receive proper educational services.

The early preparation and establishment of a school for the disabled begins with training which is not just only how to tend or care for children with disabilities, but is how to have a commitment and persistence in caring children with disability. This is a challenge for us; the commitment is needed not only from an individual standpoint but the institution as a whole. Therefore the management can be continuous; Training after training can be done and sustainable.

Our training program objective is that the rights of children with disabilities are met. We are driven with the idea that children with disabilities should be able to fulfill their rights. Our training missions include:

- Attaining and providing the caregivers and teachers of children with disabilities with the needed expertise so they have the capabilities of helping children/person with disabilities.

all learning can be carried out in collaboration

- Attaining skillful disabled to help other person/children with disabilities.
- Evaluate and monitoring the current implemented program
- Within the implemented program, interaction and solid cooperation is needed between supporting work unit, caregivers, teachers, therapist, managerial staff and the board of Management.
- The training approach towards the caregivers should be based on :
 - o How the disabled are able to completely manage their activities by their own or with minimum help/support from the caregivers/teachers.
 - o How to give an example of activities to the disabled.
 - o How to guide or direct the disabled to do one activity.

Because of the importance of increasing the quality of services towards the person/children with disabilities is an asset for the future, therefore Yayasan Sayap Ibu is committed to have an important role as a foundation and essence to the advancement of quality for the disabled within the nation.

Such is the importance of standardization and adequate services for the disabled; a breakthrough is needed in doing educational services for the disabled which is integrated, holistic and continuous. This effort is part of:

- Intervention to prevent wrong interaction and treatment for the disabled.
- Changing norm views within the society.
- Extending the support of families/caregivers/teachers/companions to improve the quality of life for the disabled.
- As an initial step towards creating work opportunity for the disabled.
- Creating a self-sufficient or self-dependent scheme for the disabled.

Yayasan Sayap Ibu is fully committed and gives its utmost effort to provide the basic needs for the disabled; to provide a favorable environment as well as making sure that the children with disabilities can receive proper and adequate education – as it is their right, and learn according to their abilities, so they can grow as an adult human being that have responsibilities or at the very least become an independent person in the society.

In the learning process, children are involved in many activities, which are adjusted based on their age and level of disability, which will help them find a new learning experience.

Learning process which means it does not happen just outside the dorm (school for example), learning process should be a good learning experience and fun both for kids, educators, caregivers and therapists and

between dormitories and schools that can happen all

at once in an institution like that has now occurred in Yayasan sayap Ibu Banten Province Branch.

Yayasan sayap Ibu Banten Province Branch, children who are in institutions in particular have had a regular schedule that is integrated between the dormitory, therapeutic and functional schools with a convenient curriculum be adapted with the variety of their disability. Many functional activities they are cooking, shopping, gardening, recreation, environmental cleaning and other routine activities.

To support our effort in providing maximum, integrated, sustainable services toward person/children with disability, Yayasan Sayap Ibu will collaborate and cooperate with:

- Central government
- Regional government
- International Social Institution which provide experts and professional caregivers/chaperone (Perkins International)
- Caregivers, Educators, Therapist and experts/professional locally and abroad.
- Society/communities

In the integrated service process in our Institution, it is proven that maximum support from the society to the disabled is crucial towards the achievement of results and the sustainability of our services to the disabled. The change from service based care to the integrated service with education and rehabilitation, have simplify the social accessibility for the disabled, in which concretely resulted in providing the disabled the opportunity to grow and develop as well as exploring the maximum potential of the disabled.

The result that soon followed, the disabled have accomplished in changing the attitude (views) and behavior of society (social function) towards more positive direction. In addition, outside society has been following the development of social services, and in their views, the service towards people/children with disabilities is improving. Another result is the changing images of the caregivers/chaperone for the disabled, from only as a regular caregiver role, it evolves to a more prestigious caregivers as well as other roles, as teachers or even as a therapist.

By giving access to education, we try to achieve our goal by fulfilling important attribute for the disabled, such as:

Personal Attribute

Through personal attribute, it is believed that every person has strength and potential in one self though that person bears disability. This strength and potential has to be recognized by the disabled and people who work with and together with the disabled have to foster and encourage that strength and potential within the disabled.

Knowledge Attribute

Through the knowledge attribute, person/children with disabilities can develop their strength and potential, also for a worker who works in the field of disabilities should encourage the disabled to use their potential and strength for a better quality of life.

Material Attribute

Through the availability of material/items, whether an equipment/tools for helping/support the day to day activities of the disabled, or the availability of common equipment/tools that can be accessed by the disabled, it is believed that these availability helps the disabled to do roles that being done by non-disabilities person because obstacle in an issue anymore, through procurement of material/items that specially designed or with modification.

Social Attribute

Social attribute empowers relationship between an individual with disabilities with other peoples and society, that is building, bridging and strengthen the social relationship between the disabled with one another, their families, and surrounding resources system.

We hope with the education process, children with disabilities can be more independent in their future life with the full support from all parts of the society.

At the end, our future commitment is to become an exemplary role model for other institutions in the integrated service program for children with disabilities, therefore person/children with disabilities in Indonesia can have better services from more than care giving and treatment.

No	Children with Disabilities, Access to Educational Process/Services	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017
1.	External Educational Process/services	13	13	5	5	5
2.	Internal Educational Process/services	0	0	21	27	27
3.	Both External and Internal Educational Process/services	0	0	6	4	4
4.	Children with no/limited access to Educational Process/services	24	24	10	4	4
Number of Children		37	37	36	36	36

2. Education within/with Sayap Ibu Foundation
3. Receive both Internal (at Sayap Ibu) and External Education process
4. Without/No Access to Education

Legend :

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